

Improving Teacher Performance Throughstrengthening Situational Leadership, Organizational Climate, And Personality

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 10, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: November 14, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : SITOREM Analysis, Teacher Performance, Situational Leadership, Organizational Climate and Personality</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5701059</p>	<p><i>This study aims to determine the strength of the variables that are thought to affect teacher performance. These variables are situational leadership, organizational climate, and personality, either individually or together with teacher performance variables. The research population is all permanent teachers of private junior high school foundations (GTJ) in Bogor Regency. The sampling technique uses Multistage Random Sampling, while the formula used to determine the number of samples is the Slovin formula, with a sample of 275. The results of the study found that the variables of situational leadership, organizational climate, and personality had a significant positive relationship with teacher performance. The following is the order of the strength of the relationship between these variables: ($r_{y1} = 0.933, <0.05$), ($r_{y2} = 0.801, <0.05$), and ($r_{y3} = 0.860, <0.05$). The results of the SITOREM analysis show that the teacher performance variables that need improvement are: (1) efficiency, relating to completing the preparation of learning outcomes assessment questions before the given time limit and carrying out information and communication technology-based learning innovations using ICT facilities available in schools, (2) effectiveness, related to implementing e-learning to improve student learning outcomes and implementing Classroom Action Research (CAR) using school funding budgets to improve student learning outcomes.</i></p>

Introduction

Teachers have a strategic role in the success of a country's education. Therefore, the competence of teachers must continue to be improved along with the times. Teachers have a very heavy workload, not only to their students but also to the state. Teachers even have a central role in realizing the goals of national education. Another program carried out to improve teacher performance is the implementation of learning by empowering high order thinking skills (HOTS) by emphasizing 21st century abilities, such as critical thinking (Critical Thinking), creative thinking (Creative Thinking), collaborative (Collaborative Thinking) and communicative (Communicative). In addition, an assessment involving the stages of higher thinking skills (Hots Assessment). Based on the description above shows that teacher performance is an important component in efforts to achieve national education goals. Thus, it is necessary to conduct research on teacher performance and its variables. The results of the preliminary survey of thirty permanent teachers of the foundation at 7 private junior high schools in Bogor Regency, have not shown satisfactory performance. The results of a preliminary survey of thirty permanent teachers of the foundation at seven private junior high schools in the Regency Bogor ters This shows that there are problems in teacher performance as described in the following:

1. There are 48.3% of teachers who have problems with work productivity, where this can be seen in reporting the increase in the results of self-development activities in the form of workshops and scientific activities such as seminars, colloquiums, panel discussions, training and education that they participate in and in creating innovative works for improve students' understanding of the subject matter.
2. There are 25% of teachers who have problems in the quality of work, which can be seen in analyzing the absorption of each student's subject matter based on the assessment of learning outcomes and in carrying out learning using methods that are in accordance with the characteristics of basic competencies.
3. There are 13.3% of teachers who have problems in the quantity of work, which can be seen from the number of teachers who have problems carrying out the main tasks each semester in the form of: planning, implementing, assessing, guiding, and training, as well as carrying out additional tasks that are inherent and in carrying out guidance services for students who have learning difficulties.
4. There are 18.3% of teachers who have problems with work efficiency, which can be seen from the number of teachers who have problems in completing the preparation of learning outcomes assessment

questions before the given time limit and in carrying out information and communication technology-based learning innovations using ICT facilities that available at school.

5. There are 51.7% of teachers who have problems in implementing e-learning to improve student learning outcomes and in carrying out Classroom Action Research (CAR) using school funding budgets to improve student learning outcomes.

Based on the theoretical study and framework of thinking that has been described previously, the following hypotheses can be formulated:

1. There is a positive relationship between situational leadership and teacher performance, so that strengthening situational leadership can improve teacher performance.
2. There is a positive relationship between organizational climate and teacher performance so that strengthening the organizational climate with teacher performance can improve teacher performance.
3. There is a positive relationship between personality and teacher performance so that personality strengthening can improve teacher performance.
4. There is a positive relationship between situational leadership and organizational climate together with teacher performance so that strengthening situational leadership and organizational climate with teacher performance can improve teacher performance.
5. There is a positive relationship between situational leadership and organizational climate with teacher performance so that strengthening situational and personality leadership can improve teacher performance.
6. There is a positive relationship between organizational climate and personality with teacher performance so that strengthening organizational climate and personality can improve teacher performance.
7. There is a positive relationship between situational leadership, organizational climate, and personality with teacher performance so that strengthening situational leadership, organizational climate, and personality can improve teacher performance.

II. METHOD

This research was conducted on private junior high school teachers in 109 schools located in Bogor Regency, West Java province from June 2021 to August 2021. The method used in this study was a correlational study which is part of the type of quantitative descriptive research, and continued with SITOREM analysis. The purpose of the correlation study is to find out the presence or absence of a relationship, how strong it is, and the direction of the relationship (positive or negative). The results of the correlational analysis are strengthened by the SITOREM analysis, until indicators are found that need to be improved and maintained or developed immediately. (Widodo Sunaryo and Sri Setyaningsih, 2018:3)The explanation of the research method carried out produces a constellation of relationships between research variables which can be described as follows:

Figure 1: Research Constellation Model

Information :

X1 = Situational Leadership Independent Variable

X2 = Organizational Climate Independent Variable

X3 = Personality Independent Variable

Y = Teacher Performance Bound Variable

The population in this study were teachers and lecturers at Private Junior High Schools (SMP) in Bogor Regency with the status of Permanent Teachers of the Private Foundation (GTY) totaling 4484 people from 774 schools. This population was chosen considering the existing limitations in terms of knowledge, time and funds, so this research was conducted limited to only schools that the researcher could reach. Determination of the sample in this study using the Slovin formula to obtain a total sample of 275. Sampling using simple random proportions or Multistage Random Sampling.

RESULT

Hypothesis testing is done by correlation and regression analysis. Testing the first, second and third hypotheses using simple correlation and regression analysis, while the fourth to seventh hypotheses use multiple correlation analysis. The results of the hypothesis test show the following results:

Table 1. Summary of Analysis of Variance of Significance Test of Regression Equation

No	Correlation	Regression Equation	Significant Test		Conclusion
			FCou nt	F _{tabl} e	
1	Y-X ₁	$\hat{Y} = -42,683+0,933.X_1$	1841. 251	3,8 76	Significan t
2	Y-X ₂	$\hat{Y}=-100,067+0,801.X_2$	488.6 40	3,8 76	Significan t
3	Y-X ₃	$\hat{Y}=-41,287+0,860.X_3$	775.9 69	3,8 76	Significan t
4	Y- X ₁ ,X ₂	$\hat{Y}=53.493+0.864X_1+0.083X_2$	935.0 90	3,0 29	Significan t
5	Y- X ₁ ,X ₃	$\hat{Y}=53.493+0.659X_1+0.366X_3$	1792. 867	3,0 29	Significan t
6	Y- X ₂ ,X ₃	$\hat{Y}=-53.943+0,423X_2+0,588X_3$	737.9 32	3,0 29	Significan t
7	Y- X ₁ ,X ₂ ,X ₃	$\hat{Y}=-70.973 + 0.611.X_1$ $+0.059.X_2 + 0.363.X_3$	1211. 028	2,6 38	Significan t

Table 2: Summary of Correlation Significance Test

No	Correlation	Correlation Coefficient	Significant Test		Conclusion
			Sig	α	
1.	Y-X ₁	$ry_1 = 0.933$	0.000	0.05	H0 is rejected, H1 is accepted. There is a positive relationship between Organizational Climate and Teacher Performance.
2.	Y-X ₂	$ry_2 = 0,801$	0.000	0.05	H0 is rejected, H1 is accepted. There is a positive relationship between transformational leadership and teacher performance
3.	Y-X ₃	$ry_3 = 0,860$	0.000	0.05	H0 is rejected, H1 is accepted. There is a positive relationship between Adversity Resilience and Teacher Performance
4.	Y- X ₁ ,X ₂	$ry_{12} = 0,934$	0.000	0.05	H0 is rejected, H1 is accepted. There is a positive relationship between Organizational Climate

					and transformational leadership with Teacher Performance
5.	Y- X ₁ ,X ₃	ry ₁₃ = 0,964	0.000	0.05	H0 is rejected, H1 is accepted. There is a positive relationship between Organizational Climate and Adversity Resilience with Teacher Performance
6.	Y- X ₂ ,X ₃	ry ₂₃ = 0,919	0.000	0.05	H0 is rejected, H1 is accepted. There is a positive relationship between transformational leadership and resilience with teacher performance
7.	Y- X ₁ ,X ₂ ,X ₃	ry ₁₂₃ = 0,965	0.000	0.05	H0 is rejected, H1 is accepted. There is a positive relationship between Organizational Climate, Transformational Leadership and Resilience with Teacher Performance

How big the strength of the relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable and to get the optimal solution from this research can be seen in the constellation of research and statistics based on Scientific Introduction Theory for Operations Research in Education Management or known as SITOREM. The results of the SITOREM (Scientific Identification Theory For Operational Research in Education) analysis (Hardienata S, 2017) show that the indicators that have a good contribution in increasing the related variable (Y) are as shown in the picture below. Based on the results of the SITOREM analysis of this study, it can be explained that the order of priority improvements that need to be improved are: 1). Delegating Style, 2). Emotional Stability, 3). Openness of Experience, 4) Agreeableness, 5) Warmth, 6) Efficient, and 7) Effectiveness, while the order maintained are: 1). Responsibilities 2). Participating Style. 3). 4) Quality. Conscientiousness 5). Quantity 6). Productivity 7). Organizational 8). Directing 9). instruct 10). Structure 11). Support 12). Extroversion 13). Rewards.

The Relationship between Situational Leadership and Teacher Performance

The results showed that there was a significant relationship between Situational Leadership and Teacher Performance. Based on the results of research with hypothesis testing, it is known that the correlation coefficient between Situational Leadership and Teacher Performance (ry₁) is 0.933 with the category having a very strong relationship. The probability value is $0.000 < 0.005$, then Ho is rejected, so it can be concluded that the correlation coefficient is significant. Thus, this study confirms that there is a significant relationship between Situational Leadership and Teacher Performance. The diversity in teacher performance related to situational leadership is reflected in the coefficient of determination of 0.871 or 87.1%, while the remaining 12.9% is influenced by other factors. The results of this study get the equation $= -42.683 + 0.933.X_1$ can be used to predict teacher performance based on organizational climate scores, it can be predicted that every 1 increase in organizational climate score will increase teacher performance by 0.933 times at a constant -42.683.

The Relationship between Organizational Climate and Teacher Performance

The results of the study which show that there is a significant relationship between organizational climate and teacher performance are interpreted that lecturers who have high transformational leadership will have an impact on high teacher performance. The strength of the relationship between organizational climate and teacher performance (ry₂) is reflected in the correlation coefficient value of 0.801 with a very strong relationship level category. The probability value (sig $0.000 < 0.05$), it can be concluded that Ho is rejected, it can be interpreted that there is a significant positive relationship between organizational climate and teacher performance. The diversity in teacher performance related to organizational climate is reflected in the coefficient of determination of 0.642 or 64.2%, while the remaining 35.8% is influenced by other factors. The results of this study get the equation $= -100.067 + 0.801.X_2$ can be used to predict teacher performance based on organizational climate scores, it can be predicted that every 1 increase in organizational climate score will increase teacher performance by 0.801 times at a constant -100.067.

The Relationship between Personality and Teacher Performance

The results of the study which show that there is a significant relationship between personality and teacher performance are interpreted that teachers who have high personalities will have an impact on high teacher performance. The strength of the relationship between personality and teacher performance is reflected in the

correlation coefficient value of 0.860 with a very strong relationship level category. The probability value (sig) $0.00 < 0.05$, it can be concluded that H_0 is rejected, it can be interpreted that there is a significant positive relationship between adversity resistance and teacher performance. The diversity in teacher performance related to resilience is reflected in the coefficient of determination of 0.740 or 74.0%, while the remaining 26.0% is influenced by other factors. The results of this study get the equation $Y = -41.287 + 0.860.X_3$ can be used to predict teacher performance based on the score of adversity. This means that the equation can be predicted that every 1 increase in the resilience score will increase the teacher's performance by 0.860 times at a constant of -41.287.

The Relationship between Situational Leadership and Organizational Climate with Teacher Performance

The results showed that there was a significant relationship between situational leadership and organizational climate together with teacher performance. The strength of the relationship between situational leadership and organizational climate is reflected in the correlation coefficient value of 0.934 with a very strong relationship category. Based on the results of the study, the correlation coefficient value of the relationship between situational leadership and organizational climate with teacher performance (r_{y12}) of 0.934 means that it has a very strong relationship level category, with a probability value (sig) of $0.000 < 0.05$ then H_0 is rejected, meaning that there is a relationship between situational leadership and organizational climate with teacher performance. Thus, this study confirms that there is a significant positive relationship between situational leadership and organizational climate with teacher performance.

The diversity in teacher performance that can be explained due to the influence of situational leadership and organizational climate is obtained from the coefficient of determination of 0.873 which means that 87.3% of teacher performance factors are determined jointly by situational leadership and organizational climate with teacher performance while 12.7% the rest is determined by other factors. The results of this study get the equation $Y = -53.493 + 0.864.X_1 + 0.083.X_2$ can be used to predict teacher performance based on situational leadership scores and organizational climate. This means that the equation can predict that every 1 increase in situational leadership scores and organizational climate will simultaneously increase teacher performance by 0.864 times for organizational situational leadership variables and 0.083 for organizational climate variables at a constant -53,493

Relationship between situational leadership and personality with teacher performance

The results showed that there was a significant positive relationship between situational and personal leadership and teacher performance. Based on the results of the study, the correlation coefficient value of the relationship between situational leadership and personality with teacher performance was obtained. (r_{y13}) of 0.964 with a strong relationship category, with a probability value (sig) $0.000 < 0.005$, then H_0 is rejected, meaning that there is a significant relationship between situational leadership and personality with teacher performance. Thus, this study confirms that there is a significant positive relationship between situational and personal leadership together with teacher performance. The contribution of situational leadership and personality to teacher performance. (r_{2y13}) of 0.929 which can be interpreted that 92.9% of teacher performance factors are determined jointly by situational leadership and personality while 7.1% is determined by other factors. The results of this study get the equation $Y = -53.493 + 0.659.X_1 + 0.366.X_3$ can be used to predict teacher performance based on situational and personal leadership scores. This means that the equation can predict that every 1 increase in situational leadership and personality scores will simultaneously increase teacher performance by 0.659 times for situational leadership variables and 0.366 times for personality variables at a constant -53,493.

Relationship between Organizational Climate and Personality with Teacher Performance.

The results showed that there was a significant positive relationship between organizational climate and personality with teacher performance. Based on the results of the study, the correlation coefficient value of the relationship between organizational climate and personality with teacher performance (r_{y23}) was 0.919 with a very strong category, with a probability value (sig) of $0.000 < 0.005$, then H_0 was rejected, meaning that there was a significant relationship between organizational climate and personality with teacher performance. Thus, this study confirms that there is a significant positive relationship between organizational climate and personality together with teacher performance. The contribution of organizational climate and personality to teacher performance (r_{2y23}) is 0.844, which means that 84.4% of teacher performance factors are determined jointly by organizational climate and personality, while the remaining 15.6% is determined by other factors. The results of this study get the equation $Y = -53.493 + 0.423.X_2 + 0.588.X_3$ can be used to predict teacher performance based on organizational climate and personality scores. This means that the equation can predict that every 1 increase in organizational climate and personality scores will simultaneously increase teacher performance by

0.423 times for the resilience variable and 0.588 times for the organizational climate and personality variables at a constant -53,493.

Relationship between Situational Leadership, Organizational Climate, and Personality with Teacher Performance

The results showed that there was a significant positive relationship between organizational climate, organizational climate, and personality with teacher performance. Based on the results of the study, the correlation coefficient value of the relationship between situational leadership, organizational climate, and personality with teacher performance (r_{y123}) was 0.965 with a very strong category, with a probability value (sig) $0.000 < 0.005$, then H_0 was rejected, meaning that there was a significant relationship between leadership situational, organizational climate, and personality with teacher performance. Thus, this study confirms that there is a significant positive relationship between situational leadership, organizational climate, and personality together with teacher performance.

The contribution of situational leadership, organizational climate, and personality to teacher performance (r^2_{y123}) is 0.931 which can be interpreted that 93.1% of diversity in teacher performance can be explained by situational leadership climate, organizational climate, and personality while the remaining 6.9% is determined by factors other.

The results of this study get the equation $= -70.973 + 0.611.X_1 + 0.059.X_2 + 0.363.X_3$ can be used to predict teacher performance based on situational leadership scores, organizational climate, and personality. This means that the equation can predict that every 1 increase in situational leadership scores, organizational climate, and personality will simultaneously increase teacher performance by 0.611 times for situational leadership variables, 0.059 times for organizational climate variables and 0.363 times for personality variables at a constant -70,973.

There are some limitations of the study that can be taken into consideration and for improvement in future research. The limitations of this research include:

Research environment restrictions. This research is specifically limited to the Permanent Desert environment of the Junior High School Foundation in Bogor Regency, so that the conclusions of this study are limited to the population of this study. A wider scope of research is needed so that the results of the research have a wider impact. The number of variables studied. This study was conducted on only three independent variables, namely situational leadership, organizational climate, and personality that affect the dependent variable, namely teacher performance, so that restrictions on the dependent variable of teacher performance are also limited to its relationship with the three independent variables of situational leadership, organizational climate, and personality. Understanding of teacher performance is limited from the independent variables studied only. So, for a more comprehensive understanding, further research is needed regarding other variables, such as situational leadership, organizational climate, personality, organizational culture, transformational leadership, and integrity. The science of management and organization is dynamic, its development is very fast so that in the future new concepts will appear regarding the variables in this research and other variables that will experience changes and progress. While this research uses theories of teacher performance, situational leadership, organizational climate, and personality which have limited implications for the concepts used today.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the study, it can be concluded that this study has found efforts to improve the performance of permanent teachers of Private Junior High School Foundations (SMP) in Bogor Regency through strengthening of regional leadership, organizational climate, and personality, based on the following identification: There is a significant positive relationship between situational leadership and teacher performance. By strengthening situational leadership can improve teacher performance. There is a significant positive relationship between organizational climate and teacher performance. Thus strengthening the organizational climate can improve teacher performance. There is a significant positive relationship between personality and teacher performance. Thus, personality strengthening can improve teacher performance. There is a significant positive relationship between situational leadership and organizational climate together with teacher performance, thus strengthening situational leadership and organizational climate together can improve teacher performance. There is a significant positive relationship between situational leadership and personality together with teacher performance. Thus strengthening situational leadership and personality together can improve teacher performance. There is a significant positive relationship between organizational climate and personality together with teacher performance. Thus strengthening the organizational climate and personality together can improve teacher performance.

The findings of this study produce findings that must be improved so that teacher performance increases to the maximum. Suggestions for indicators that are already good are suggested to be maintained, while indicators that

are not good are to be improved. Based on this research, it is safe for school principals to improve the performance of permanent foundation teachers at Private Junior High Schools in Bogor Regency, West Java Province as follows: The principal as the head of the educational unit organizational unit must delegate authority by considering the abilities and responsibilities of his subordinates. so that the work can be completed properly, correctly, and on time. The principal as the head of the education unit must set an example to be calm, free from negative feelings, persistent, confident, have a firm stand. The principal as the leader of the education unit must reflect an individual who is broad-minded, creative, curious, intelligent, has broad interests and is willing to take risks, open to various stimuli. The principal as an education unit leader must have a warm, kind, cooperative, sympathetic, helpful, polite, trusted attitude, rama h, harmonious, forgiving, tolerant.

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